

MEASUREMENT OF RESIDUAL STRESS IN THICK THERMOSET COMPOSITE LAMINATE PLATES USING DEEP HOLE DRILLING METHOD

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ABSTRACT

To experimentally quantify the residual stresses in thick composite laminates, deep hole drilling technique is used. This method relies on the measurement of strain relaxation resulting from material removal. First, a small hole is drilled in a plate consisting of 80 layers of glass/epoxy ply. The diameter of the hole is measured. Then, the changes in the hole diameter due to the stress relaxation by trepanning a core from around the hole are re-measured. Finite element analyses are carried out to provide distortion coefficients, which are material dependent for far field applied stresses. Residual stresses are determined through the combination of numerical and experimental approach. Finally, the experimental results are compared to the numerical results. The general trend of the evolution of stresses in the numerical work has an acceptable agreement with the experimental data in the case of both unidirectional and cross-ply composite plates.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is worth mentioning that deep hole drilling technique is first used to measure residual stresses for metallic materials and is mainly suitable for thick components considering the non-uniformity of the stress distribution through the thickness. Afterwards, it has been extended to orthotropic materials. The development and background theory associated to the residual stress analysis in deep hole drilling technique from previous studies is shown below.

Deep-hole drilling technique initially was developed to evaluate the residual stress in steel welds. A 8mm diameter hole was drilled followed by trepanning out a 40 mm core incrementally [1], [2]. In order to provide a very smooth and straight 3.175 mm diameter hole, Beaney [3] recommended gun drilling method. The diameter measurements were also conducted at 0°, 45° and 90° at different intervals of 2 mm in depth through the thickness. Then a larger diameter around the hole was trepanned using an Electro Chemical Machining (ECM). The diameter variations before and after trepanning were measured through two strain gages along sides of the hole. Later, Proctor and Beaney [4] updated the method by averaging the residual stresses in the smallest area. The introduction of the non-contacting capacitance gages also led to an improvement in the methodology in their studies.

Residual stresses in steel weldments were measured by drilling two blind holes on the opposite faces of the sample. Then, strain gages were installed inside the holes and on the two faces. Lastly, the stresses were obtained after trepanning of two 32mm diameter cores. Furthermore, an experimental procedure comprising drilling in 8mm diameter hole and measuring deformations using strain gages on the hole surface was introduced. Three orthogonal gauges were used at each measurement depth to measure the stress [2].

Kingston [5] modified the machining processes of the deep-hole method to extend the applicability of the technique, to consider both thicker and thinner components. In order to carry out on-site machining on large components, a portable machine was also utilized.

More improvements in deep hole drilling method have been made by Smith and co-workers [6], [7]. They made a hole of 3 mm using a gun-drill and measuring the diameter with an air probe, which enables the measurement of the diameter at any location along the drilled hole. It is notable that the rosette strain gage is unsuitable for thick components, since the measured strain changes by the rosette strain gages become smaller as the depth of the hole increases.

Bateman et al. [1] extended this technique to orthotropic composite laminates. They used deep-hole drilling technique to determine the residual stresses in 22 mm laminate plate that were built up using a resin film infusion process from plies of a carbon non-crimp fabric (NCF) and epoxy film resin. In their method, a small hole of 3.2 mm is first drilled using a gun drill and trepanned a 14 mm diameter core by a diamond saw around the hole. The resulting residual stresses from measurements have a maximum value of about 40MPa in the fiber direction and 10MPa in the transverse direction.

Garza et al. [8] also used the deep hole drilling technique for an AS4/8552 composite laminate of 18 mm in thickness. They used the gun drill to make a 3 mm hole and utilized diamond hole saw to make a 10 mm diameter core in the laminate. The measurements showed that the highest and lowest predicted compressive stresses in the x direction are respectively of the order of 20 and 65 MPa in the 0° and 90° layers. However, the expected stresses in the y direction remained approximately on 36-38 MPa.

2 DEEP HOLE TECHNIQUE FOR ORTHOTROPIC MATERIALS

Lekhnitskii [9] studied the stress distribution in an orthotropic plate containing a hole of radius a which is under far-field direct stresses. His technique was developed based on the assumption that the thickness of the sample can be divided into a number of stacked plates without any shear stress between adjacent plates shown in Figure 1. Each of these independent plates then can be considered as an individual infinite plate with a hole utilized to evaluate three in-plane components of stress through the thickness as illustrated in Figure 2. In the formula of his work, the center of the hole is considered as the origin of coordinates and the directions of the axes X and Y taken as the principal directions of elasticity. Equation (1) shows the closed form solution recommended by Lekhnitskii when a uniform far-field stress P is applied at an angle of φ relative to the material principal direction shown in Figure 3. Thus, the stress distribution could be obtained at different angles around a hole based on this equation.

Figure 1: Assumed stacked plates.

Figure 2: Schematic of an individual infinite plate representative of each single plate divided through the thickness.

$$\sigma_r(\theta) = P \frac{E_\theta}{E_1} [(1 - \cos^2 \varphi + (k + n) \sin^2 \varphi) k \cos^2 \theta + ((1 + n) \cos^2 \varphi - k \sin^2 \varphi) \sin^2 \theta - n(1 + k + n) \sin \varphi \cos \varphi \sin \theta \cos \theta] \quad (1)$$

Where $\sigma_r(\theta)$ and E_θ are respectively the radial stress and the tangential Young's modulus of the material, associated with the elastic constants for the principal directions shown in the Equation (2).

$$\frac{1}{E_\theta} = \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{E_1} + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_1} \right) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + \frac{\cos^4 \theta}{E_2} \quad (2)$$

Here, all ν_{12} , E_1 , E_2 and G_{12} are the Poisson coefficient, Young's moduli and the modulus of shear for the principal directions respectively.

Figure 3: Schematic of an orthotropic plate under far-field stress.

When the stress is applied in the material principal direction of X , then $\varphi = 0$ and P can be considered as σ_x , so that Equation (1) can be rewritten as Equation (3).

$$\sigma_r(\theta) = \sigma_x \frac{E_\theta}{E_1} [-k_1 \cos^2 \theta + (1 + n_1) \sin^2 \theta] \quad (3)$$

In this equation, k_1 and n_1 are obtained as following equations:

$$n_1 = \sqrt{\left[2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}} - \nu_{12} \right) + \frac{E_1}{G_{12}} \right]} \quad (4)$$

$$k_1 = \sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}}$$

However, in Equation (1), in the case of $P = \sigma_y$ in the material direction of Y ($\varphi = 90$) the radial stress distribution is according to Equation (5).

$$\sigma_r(\theta) = \sigma_y \frac{E_\theta}{E_1} [-k_2 \cos^2 \theta + (1 + n_2) \sin^2 \theta] \quad (5)$$

Where k_2 and n_2 are according to Equation (6).

$$n_2 = \sqrt{\left[2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_2}{E_1}} - \nu_{21} \right) + \frac{E_2}{G_{21}} \right]} \quad (6)$$

$$k_2 = \sqrt{\frac{E_2}{E_1}}$$

The radial displacement, U_θ , is expressed by Equation (7) in the loading direction and the change in the diameter normal to the loading direction.

$$\overline{U_r(\theta = 0)} = -\frac{\sigma_y}{\sqrt{E_2 E_1}} r \quad (7)$$

$$\overline{U_r(\theta = 90)} = \frac{\sigma_y}{E_2} r (1 + n_2)$$

Lekhnitskii's analysis can be used to calculate the coefficients of matrix M including $f(\theta_i)$, $g(\theta_i)$ as expressed in Equation (8). However, his work is not capable of providing $h(\theta_i)$ coefficient corresponding to the far-field shear stress (Figure 2). Hence, the finite element method which is discussed in the next section of this work rather than Lekhnitskii's analysis needs to be used to generate the coefficients including $f(\theta_i)$, $g(\theta_i)$, $h(\theta_i)$ for an orthotropic material.

$$f(\theta_i) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \sqrt{\left[2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}} - \nu_{12} \right) + \frac{E_1}{G_{12}} \right]} - \sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}} \right] + \frac{\cos 2\theta_i}{2} \left[1 + \sqrt{\left[2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}} - \nu_{12} \right) + \frac{E_1}{G_{12}} \right]} + \sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$g(\theta_i) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(1 + \sqrt{2 \left(\frac{E_2}{E_1} - \nu_{21} \right) + \frac{E_2}{G_{21}}} \right) \frac{E_1}{E_2} - \sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}} \right] - \frac{\cos 2\theta_i}{2} \left[\left(1 + \sqrt{2 \left(\frac{E_2}{E_1} - \nu_{21} \right) + \frac{E_2}{G_{21}}} \right) \frac{E_1}{E_2} + \sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}} \right]$$

Equation (9) is used to calculate the residual stress in an orthotropic material based on Equation (1). M is the material dependent coefficient that is calculated numerically in the next section and compared to that obtained from Lekhnitskii's analytical approach. However, the analytical method does not provide $h(\theta_i)$ under shear load presented in Figure 2.

$$\bar{\sigma} = -E_1 [M]^* \overline{U_r(\theta)} \quad (9)$$

Where the normalized displacements and stress vectors are:

$$\overline{U_r(\theta)} = \begin{bmatrix} \overline{U_r(\theta_1)} \\ \vdots \\ \overline{U_r(\theta_i)} \\ \vdots \\ \overline{U_r(\theta_N)} \end{bmatrix} \quad \bar{\sigma} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad M = \begin{bmatrix} f(\theta_1) & g(\theta_1) & h(\theta_1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ f(\theta_i) & g(\theta_i) & h(\theta_i) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ f(\theta_N) & g(\theta_N) & h(\theta_N) \end{bmatrix}$$

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

As discussed, since there are not suitable close-form solutions for orthotropic materials unlike the isotropic ones, a finite element approach needs to be used to obtain the distortion coefficients including, $f(\theta_i)$, $g(\theta_i)$ and $h(\theta_i)$ represented through the matrix M expressed in eq.(9). To obtain these coefficients, three separate finite element analyses under far-field stresses of σ_x , σ_y and σ_{xy} are carried out as described in Figure 4 considering the principal material direction. For this purpose, the FEM analyses using a 2-D plane stress with S8R elements are conducted in ABAQUS commercial software. The geometry of the finite element mesh is shown in Figure 5. As can be seen, a hole of 10 mm diameter compared to the size of the mesh in a plate of 100 mm by 100 mm is small enough. Hence, the analyses can be considered close to those in an infinite plate. The material properties obtained from experiment presented in Table 1 are used for these analyses. Also, these properties are used to obtain the analytical distortion coefficients of $f(\theta_i)$ and $g(\theta_i)$ in matrix M presented in Equation (9). As discussed above and seen in Figure 6, the shear stress case cannot be compared because Lekhnitskii only provided an analysis for the direct stresses. It is also clear from Figure 6 that both plots of radial distortions follow the same trend as those obtained from analytical calculations.

Figure 4: Far-field stresses applied to the mesh with respect to the principal material direction.

Figure 5: Geometry of the finite element mesh

Material	Value (GPa) [10]
E_1	49.93
E_2	10.95
G_{12}	4.27
ν_{12}	0.3

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of FX E773/S-2 Glass.

a)

b)

Figure 6: Finite element and analytical calculation for normalized radial deformation versus angle at the edge of the hole under far-field stress a) σ_x b) σ_y . c) σ_{xy}

According to the finite element and Lekhnitskii's analysis, the distortion coefficients including $f(\theta_i)$, $g(\theta_i)$ and $h(\theta_i)$ are according to Equations (10) and (11) respectively. Note that the analytical equations presented in Equation (11) are obtained utilizing material properties of Table 1 and Equation (8). As it is apparent, there is an acceptable agreement between the coefficients.

$$\begin{aligned} f(\theta_i) &= 1.429 + 3.541 \cos 2\theta_i \\ g(\theta_i) &= 4.524 - 6.672 \cos 2\theta_i \\ h(\theta_i) &= 0.439 \sin 2\theta_i \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(\theta_i) &= 1.424 + 3.364 \cos 2\theta_i \\ g(\theta_i) &= 4.524 - 6.312 \cos 2\theta_i \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

4 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES AND RESULTS

The deep hole drilling method which was developed based on the above theoretical background utilized composite plates of 150 mm × 150 mm with the thickness of 18.28 mm. Also, the composite laminate was manufactured using the hand-lay-up made up of 80 layers and cured in an auto-clave to produce the final part. The residual stresses are measured in the unidirectional, $[0_{40}]_S$, and cross-ply, $[0_{10}, 90_{10}]_{2S}$, composite plates. Figure 7 illustrates the layer arrangement and composite laminate after conducting the deep hole drilling.

Figure 7: Schematic of the specimens' layer sequence in unidirectional a) cross-ply b) laminates.

The DHD technique is divided into four steps. After drilling a reference hole of 3 mm diameter using the computer numerically controlled machine (CNC), the reference hole is mapped angularly at each 15 degrees using the coordinate measure machine (CMM) by moving back and forth from the center of the hole to the edge. During the process, the measurement starts from the surface of the specimen through the thickness axially at each 0.2 mm intervals, leading to 24 angular locations at each 85 axial positions. This increment coincides along angles of 0°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 90°, 135°, 180°, etc. Afterwards, the diameters are calculated for each angle. Then, a column of material incrementally at

each 2 mm through the thickness, using the center of the reference hole as its axis leaving an intact core is trepanned. Finally, to calculate the radial strain relaxation, the measurements are repeated at the same locations around the hole and through the thickness as before trepanning. The measured radii, then, are added up to calculate the diameters. The released radial deformations, $U_r(\theta)$, therefore, are obtained from the difference of the diameters before and after trepanning. Finally, the residual stress distributions are determined using the radial distortions (Equation (12)) and distortion coefficients obtained from the finite element analyses illustrated in Equation (10).

$$\overline{U_r(\theta)} = \frac{(a_{a\theta'} + a_{a\theta}) - (a_{b\theta'} + a_{b\theta})}{2a_0} \tag{12}$$

Where $a_{a\theta'}$, $a_{a\theta}$ and $a_{b\theta'}$, $a_{b\theta}$ are respectively the radius of the hole after and before trepanning at each angular position θ and its counter point θ' which were added to calculate the diameter values. a_0 is the nominal radius of the hole (1.5 mm). Also, the location of the holes were considered far enough from the edges as can be seen in Figure 8 and to assure the accuracy and repeatability of the hole measurements two holes were drilled. Both holes were suitable for measurements. Also, an example of the diameter variation for 45° and 135° angular positions in cross-ply laminate plate and for 0° and 30° before and after trepanning is displayed in Figure 9 and Figure 10. As it is seen in the case of cross-ply laminate plate, the diameter changes follow the stacking sequence through the thickness for these locations. The variation of the diameter for unidirectional laminate plate is also demonstrated in Figure 11.

Figure 8: Schematic of location of holes in residual stress measurement.

Figure 9: Diameter variation through the thickness for direction $\theta=45^\circ$ in the cross-ply plate

Figure 10: Diameter variation through the thickness for direction $\theta=135^\circ$ in the cross-ply laminate plate.

Figure 11: Diameter variation for 3 mm diameter hole in the unidirectional laminate plate along the thickness for direction a) $\theta=0^\circ$, b) $\theta=30^\circ$.

The radial distortions for the cross-ply and unidirectional calculated from the measured difference in diameter illustrated in Equation (12), are plotted in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

Figure 12: Radial distortion for a hole of 3 mm diameter in the unidirectional laminate plate along the thickness for the direction a) $\theta=0^\circ$, b) $\theta=30^\circ$.

Figure 13: Radial distortion for a hole of 3 mm diameter in the cross-ply plate across the thickness for direction a) $\theta=45^\circ$, b) $\theta=135^\circ$.

Finally, combining the acquired distortion from experiment with material dependent coefficients from the simulation results enables us to estimate the residual stresses through the thickness of these composite plates. As seen previously, combining the acquired distortion from experiment with material dependent coefficients from simulation results enables us to estimate the residual stresses through the thickness of these composite plates. For this purpose, Equation (12) was used to calculate different stress components. Also, the residual stress graphs for σ_x , σ_y and σ_{xy} in the unidirectional and the cross-ply laminates are shown in Figure 14. The global xy direction have been used rather than define the stress components using the ply directions. Hence, the σ_x within 90° plies is the transverse stress while for 0° plies σ_x is in the fiber direction. However, σ_x and σ_y stresses align with the principal and perpendicular direction in the unidirectional laminate respectively.

For the unidirectional laminate plate, the results indicates that the highest in-plane transverse residual stress, σ_y is of the order of 3 MPa in compression nearest the surface of the laminate. While, it is roughly 2.5 MPa in tensile at the mid-thickness. The maximum longitudinal stress, σ_x , shows fairly higher values in tension and compression with the value of 7 MPa and 15 MPa respectively in the middle and upper plies. The calculated shear stress has very low value throughout the entire laminate. For the cross-ply laminate plate, the highest transverse residual stress, σ_x , is of the order of 42 MPa for the set of 90° plies in tension. While, the compressive stress value in the fiber direction for 0° plies is roughly 38 MPa and 18 MPa respectively near the upper and lower boundary. The highest stress components of σ_y in 0° plies in the transverse direction are up to about 13 MPa within the plies near the bottom of the plate in tension. However, the compressive stresses in fiber direction within the 90° plies are relatively small up to 5 MPa occurs at the mid-thickness.

Figure 14: In-plane residual stress in a) unidirectional b) cross-ply laminate plate.

The experimental results in Figure 15 were compared with numerically calculated in-plane macroscopic transverse residual stresses in a unidirectional laminate. Therefore, it was found from the results that the maximum residual stress in the unidirectional specimen is about 6% of the unidirectional ply strength in the x and y direction. However, for the cross-ply case, about 12% of the material strength

for tensile stresses in the y direction (which is in the transverse direction within 0° plies) should be considered as the residual stress. However, since the material strength under compressive stress in y direction is almost 4 times larger than that in the same direction in tension, the residual stress should be taken roughly 6%. This value in the unidirectional case is almost 2% of the strength. Thus, it is apparent that for the unidirectional laminate plate, the stress level is relatively lower than that for the cross-ply laminate for all components and on the whole, the results show that the process-induced residual stresses are not significant in the case of unidirectional laminate. This is due to the dissimilar mechanical and thermal properties of the adjacent plies in cross-ply laminate plate compared to the unidirectional case leading to higher stress values during the curing process.

Figure 15: In-plane residual stress in a) unidirectional b) cross-ply laminate plate.

5 CONCLUSION

The residual stresses particularly in-situ measurements are hard to quantify; however, the deep hole drilling technique previously has been used to measure the residual stress in thick isotropic material. It was extended to be utilized in an orthotropic material. After measuring the distortions through CMM in an 18 mm thick glass/epoxy laminate composite plate, the numerical analysis was used to convert already measured strains to stresses. The calculated stresses and measured strains from the experiment were compared with theoretical ones. It was shown that the trend of changes for both data are in good agreement. Measurements show that the maximum stresses are associated with the cross-ply laminate with the magnitude of 42 MPa for the set of 90° plies in tension and roughly 38 MPa in compression in the fiber direction for 0° plies. For the unidirectional case, the largest in-plane transverse residual stress, σ_y is of the order of 3 MPa in compression and 2.5 MPa in tensile.

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